

Advancing Spatio-Temporal Forecasting of Vegetation with Extended Context and Climate-Aware Learning

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Abstract

Accurate vegetation forecasting from Earth observation data is essential for understanding ecosystem dynamics under changing environmental conditions. While recent deep learning models achieve strong performance on standardized benchmarks, it remains unclear whether these results generalize to more realistic settings with irregular temporal sampling. In this study, we apply the Contextformer model to GeoClimaData, a multi-year EO-climate dataset, using an anchor-based data loader that enables flexible sequence construction. We systematically vary key input design choices, including context length, meteorological conditioning, and temporal and spatial encoding. Results show that the model remains effective under irregular sampling and consistently outperforms a persistence baseline. Longer context windows yield modest improvements, while extended meteorological aggregation degrades performance. Explicit seasonal encoding and spatial encoding provide limited additional benefit. These findings highlight the importance of input design when transferring benchmark-driven models to real-world Earth observation data.

Keywords: vegetation forecasting, spatio-temporal deep learning, earth observation time series

1. Introduction

Accurate forecasting of vegetation dynamics from Earth observation (EO) data is essential for anticipating environmental change and supporting data-driven decision-making in ecology, agriculture, and land management (Liou et al. 2020, Pettorelli et al. 2014). Sentinel-2 imagery, with its high spatial resolution and frequent revisit time, offers unique opportunities for predictive analysis but is often hindered by cloud cover and irregular temporal sampling,

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complicating the use of image time series in forecasting applications (Drusch et al. 2012, Meraner et al. 2020).

Recent advances in data-driven forecasting have demonstrated that deep learning models can learn complex spatio-temporal dependencies directly from EO data, offering an alternative to traditional process-based or empirical vegetation models (Moskollai et al. 2021). In this context, the EarthNet2021 Challenge introduced a standardized benchmark for Earth surface forecasting, enabling systematic comparison of model architectures under controlled conditions (Requena-Mesa et al. 2021). Building on this framework, Benson et al. (2024) proposed the GreenEarthNet dataset and the Contextformer model, a multi-modal transformer architecture that integrates Sentinel-2 imagery with meteorological drivers to forecast fine-resolution vegetation dynamics.

While highly effective for benchmarking model architectures, EarthNet-style datasets impose strong constraints on the temporal structure of the data. Fixed-length sequences, regular sampling intervals, and short historical windows are intentionally enforced to ensure comparability across models, but they also limit the exploration of longer ecological memory effects, multi-seasonal dynamics, and alternative input configurations (Koochfar & Dietz 2023, Schmitt et al. 2023). As a result, it remains unclear to what extent models developed under such standardized settings remain applicable when these assumptions are relaxed in more realistic scenarios.

This work investigates whether performance gains attributed to modern EO forecasting architectures remain robust under such relaxed conditions. We address this question by applying the Contextformer model (Benson et al. 2024) to GeoClimaData, a flexible, long-term EO-climate dataset recently developed by Apolo-Apolo et al. (in prep.). Rather than modifying the model architecture, we adapt the input construction through a flexible, anchor-based data loader that generates EarthNet-compatible sequences from multi-year Sentinel-2 and ERA5-Land time series. The design of this loader is motivated by both data characteristics and process-based considerations. In practice, strict cloud filtering leads to irregular temporal sampling, which introduces variable gaps between observations. At the same time, ecological and climate-driven processes, such as vegetation responses to climate variability and change, operate across multiple temporal scales, extending beyond the intra-annual windows typically considered in the literature (Linscheid et al. 2020). The proposed loader enables the model to accommodate these conditions while preserving compatibility with the original benchmark setup.

This framework enables us to explicitly address the following research questions: (1) do transformers, like Contextformer, remain effective when applied to irregularly sampled EO time series, (2) does extending the historical context window improve predictive performance by capturing longer ecological memory, (3) how does the representation of time, through relative positional encodings versus explicit seasonal encoding, affect model performance, and (4) what is the impact of incorporating explicit spatial information through geographic encoding?

Our overarching objective is to disentangle the effects of data representation and model architecture in vegetation forecasting. By systematically varying input design while keeping the model fixed, we investigate how choices such as context length, meteorological conditioning, and spatio-temporal encoding influence model behavior and performance. This work provides empirical insight into how benchmark-driven models generalize beyond controlled settings, and

highlights the importance of input design in applying deep learning models to realistic EO time series.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Task

The task is to forecast future vegetation dynamics expressed as Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) imagery. Given a sequence of past Sentinel-2 observations, static environmental variables, and meteorological drivers, the model predicts NDVI for a fixed future horizon. Formally, we predict future vegetation states ($\hat{V}^{T+1:T+K}$) conditioned on past satellite imagery ($S^{1:T}$), meteorological variables ($C^{T-M+1:T+K}$), and static topographic information (E):

$$(\hat{V}^{T+1:T+K}) = f(S^{1:T}, C^{T-M+1:T+K}, E)$$

where T denotes the length of the historical context window, $K = 20$ the prediction horizon, and M the length of the meteorological conditioning period. While the prediction horizon is kept consistent with GreenEarthNet to retain partial comparability, both T and M are varied to study the impact of longer context and climate memory.

2.2. Data: GeoClimaData

GeoClimaData is a global, analysis-ready dataset that integrates Sentinel-2 surface reflectance imagery with daily ERA5-Land meteorological variables and static environmental layers such as ESA WorldCover and Copernicus DEM (Apolo-Apolo et al. in prep.). The dataset consists of HDF5 data cubes for 48,065 globally distributed locations, each covering the period 2018-2024.

Compared to GreenEarthNet, GeoClimaData introduces three key characteristics relevant for forecasting experiments. First, Sentinel-2 imagery is subjected to strict upstream cloud filtering, retaining only scenes with less than 1% cloud cover, which minimizes residual cloud artifacts but results in irregular temporal sampling. Second, the multi-year temporal extent enables the exploration of seasonal and interannual vegetation dynamics beyond short growing-season windows. Third, the global spatial coverage increases ecological and climatic diversity across biomes and land-use regimes.

These properties make GeoClimaData well-suited for investigating vegetation forecasting under realistic data availability constraints, while retaining standardized spatial tiles that enable reproducible model training.

2.3. Model and anchor-based data construction

Our approach builds on the Contextformer architecture introduced by Benson et al. (2024), a multi-modal transformer model designed for fine-resolution vegetation forecasting. Contextformer combines a vision backbone for Sentinel-2 imagery with a temporal transformer that models the evolution of local spatial patches over time, while incorporating meteorological information through a dedicated encoder (*Figure 1*). We retain the original loss function,

aggregated meteorological encoding strategy, and delta-prediction scheme, ensuring that architectural changes do not confound our analysis.

To enable training on GeoClimaData, we introduce an anchor-based data loader that dynamically constructs EarthNet-compatible input sequences from irregularly sampled time series. At each training epoch, a sequence of consecutive cloud-free Sentinel-2 observations is selected as anchor dates. For each anchor date, a spatio-temporal data cube is assembled by pairing the Sentinel-2 image and static variables (DEM and location) with a configurable window of preceding meteorological observations. This procedure results in sequences that match the expected input structure of Contextformer, while relaxing the assumption of fixed temporal spacing between images.

Using this data loader, we systematically vary the length of the historical context window (10, 20, and 40 timesteps) and the temporal span of meteorological conditioning (5 days, 31 days, and 365 days). Temporal information is encoded either implicitly through relative positional encodings, following the original EarthNet formulation, or explicitly via a day-of-year representation that provides seasonal context to the model. In addition, an optional spatial encoding of latitude and longitude is introduced to supply geographic context.

By keeping the model architecture unchanged and modifying only the input construction and temporal representation, this setup enables a controlled analysis of how input design choices affect vegetation forecasting performance under non-standardized data conditions.

Figure 1. Adapted from Benson et al. (2024). Overview of the extended Contextformer architecture for multi-step vegetation forecasting.

2.4. Evaluation

Following the evaluation framework of Benson et al. (2024), we evaluate model predictions on a held-out test set (5% of the data) by comparing predicted and target NDVI at the pixel-time level over the forecast horizon only. We exclude context timesteps since these are not predicted. We compute four standard environmental metrics on all valid (prediction, target) pairs:

- RMSE: root mean squared error

- R^2 : squared Pearson correlation coefficient
- NSE: Nash-Sutcliffe efficiency (Nash & Sutcliffe 1970), $NSE = 1 - \text{MSE}(V, \hat{V})/\text{Var}(V)$
- $|\text{bias}|$: absolute bias, $|\bar{\hat{V}} - \bar{V}|$

A model is considered significantly better than the baseline if it improves with at least 0.05 for NSE and R^2 and decreases with 0.01 for RMSE and $|\text{bias}|$.

2.5. Baselines and ablations

We employ two complementary baselines. First, we use a persistence baseline, in which each forecasted NDVI frame is set equal to the last observed NDVI frame in the context window. Second, to isolate the impact of input design choices, we define a reference model by reproducing the default configuration of Benson et al. (2024), including the context length, meteorological input window, and spatio-temporal encoding. Starting from this reference configuration, we perform one-factor-at-a-time ablations, where each design variable is modified independently while all other settings are held fixed. This approach isolates the marginal effect of each component on predictive performance and enables direct comparison with the paper-faithful reference. *Table 1* provides an overview of all ablation configurations and their corresponding input settings.

Configuration	Context length	Meteorological window	Temporal encoding	Spatial encoding
Reference	10 steps	5 days	TP	No
Context_20	20 steps	5 days	TP	No
Context_40	40 steps	5 days	TP	No
Meteo_31	10 steps	31 days	TP	No
Meteo_365	10 steps	365 days	TP	No
Encoding_DOY	10 steps	5 days	DOY	No
Encoding_TP_Spat	10 steps	5 days	TP	Yes

Table 1. Overview of input configurations used in the ablation study. Each row varies a single input design parameter relative to the reference configuration. Parameters include context length (number of input timesteps), meteorological window (days of preceding weather data), temporal encoding (temporal positional encoding (TP) or day-of-year encoding (DOY)), and the inclusion of spatial encoding (latitude and longitude).

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Baseline and ablation comparison

All evaluated configurations outperform the persistence baseline across nearly all metrics (*Table 2*), confirming that the model effectively leverages both spatial and meteorological context beyond simple persistence.

Context Length. Increasing the context length from 10 to 20 and 40 timesteps results in marginal performance improvements. The longest context (40 timesteps) achieves the highest R^2

(0.51) and lowest RMSE (0.12), indicating that additional temporal context can improve predictive skill. However, the gains are limited. One possible explanation is that longer context windows reduce the number of available training samples, as sequences with insufficient cloud-free observations are excluded. The trade-off between context richness and data availability may constrain the benefits of longer temporal inputs. This finding is consistent with recent work on long-context time series transformers, which shows that increasing context length can improve forecasting performance by capturing long-range dependencies, although gains may diminish or become unstable at very large temporal scales due to increased noise and training complexity (Liu et al. 2025).

Meteorological conditioning. Previous work on EarthNet-style datasets has consistently highlighted the importance of meteorological inputs for vegetation and land surface forecasting, with weather information shown to be a key driver of predictive performance (Benson et al. 2024, Diaconu et al. 2022). However, these studies do not explicitly investigate how the temporal representation of meteorological inputs affects model behaviour.

In our experiments, extending the meteorological conditioning window from 5 to 31 days results in comparable performance, whereas a 365-day window leads to a substantial degradation across all metrics (RMSE = 0.17, $R^2 = 0.15$). A likely explanation lies in the aggregation strategy: meteorological variables are summarised using minimum, maximum, and mean values, such that longer windows increasingly smooth out short-term variability. In the 365-day case, the input effectively collapses to a coarse annual climatology, removing the temporal variability that is critical for modelling vegetation dynamics.

This behaviour is consistent with findings from time series modelling, where long input sequences do not necessarily improve performance if the relevant temporal signal is obscured. In long-term forecasting settings, useful dependencies can be obscured when different temporal patterns (e.g. seasonal trends and short-term fluctuations) are mixed or smoothed, making it harder for models to identify which parts of the signal are informative (Wu et al. 2021). Similarly, using excessively large or fixed temporal contexts can introduce noise by including irrelevant or weakly related observations (Koochfar & Dietz 2023). Taken together, these results suggest that the benefit of meteorological conditioning is not solely determined by the presence of climate information, but by how well its temporal structure aligns with the underlying ecological processes.

Temporal encoding. Replacing temporal positional encoding (TP) with day-of-year (DOY) encoding leads to a marked decrease in performance (RMSE = 0.18, NSE = -1.10, $|\text{bias}| = 0.12$). This result is counterintuitive, as explicit seasonal information was expected to be beneficial. One possible explanation is that seasonal information is already implicitly encoded in the meteorological inputs, which strongly drive the seasonal component of vegetation dynamics (Linscheid et al. 2020), thereby reducing the additional benefit of explicitly encoding day-of-year information. Alternatively, the multi-harmonic sinusoidal representation used for DOY encoding may impose a simplified periodic structure that does not align with the inherently multi-scale and non-stationary nature of vegetation dynamics. Earth observation signals reflect a mixture of processes acting at different temporal scales, where dominant seasonal cycles can obscure shorter- and longer-term variability (Linscheid et al. 2020). As a result, explicit harmonic

encoding of seasonality may introduce redundancy or noise rather than facilitating learning. Further investigation is required to disentangle these effects.

Spatial encoding. Including spatial encoding (latitude and longitude) has limited impact on overall performance, with only minor improvements observed in NSE. This suggests that spatial information provides little additional benefit when meteorological inputs are already available, as these may implicitly encode geographic variability. A similar pattern has been observed in prior work on Earth surface forecasting, where model contributions from meteorological inputs exceed spatial context and static features such as elevation (Diaconu et al. 2022). More generally, previous studies have noted that although spatial context can be informative, its contribution is often secondary to temporal dynamics, which tend to dominate vegetation forecasting tasks (Benson et al. 2024). Together, these findings indicate that while spatial information may be useful in principle, its added value can be limited when dynamic environmental drivers are already provided, suggesting redundancy under the current model and input design

Configuration	RMSE↓	R ² ↑	NSE↑	bias ↓
Persistence	0.22 ±0.01	0.00 ±0.00	-1.70 ±0.27	0.14 ±0.01
Reference	0.13	0.49	-0.45	0.06
Context_20	0.13	0.50	-0.38	0.06
Context_40	0.12	0.51	-0.38	0.05
Meteo_31	0.13	0.51	-0.54	0.06
Meteo_365	0.17	0.15	-1.70	0.07
Encoding_DOY	0.18	0.47	-1.10	0.12
Encoding_TP_Spat	0.13	0.49	-0.31	0.06

Table 2. Quantitative performance of the baseline and ablation configurations across evaluation metrics (RMSE, R², NSE, |bias|). Each configuration modifies a single input design parameter relative to the reference model. Due to differences in the number of valid tiles across configurations, the persistence baseline is computed separately for each configuration and reported as the mean ± standard deviation.

3.2 Qualitative assessment

Figure 2 shows the temporal evolution of predicted and target mean NDVI for a representative tile. The model captures the overall seasonal trends and interannual variability well, with predictions closely following the target NDVI even at longer lead times. However, this agreement at the aggregated level does not necessarily translate to accurate spatial predictions. Inspection of predicted images indicates that spatial patterns often remain biased towards the last observed context frame, particularly when vegetation patterns change rapidly. This indicates that, despite good performance in terms of mean NDVI, the model may still rely heavily on the most recent observation when predicting spatial structure.

Nevertheless, *Figure 3* demonstrates that the model is still capable of predicting some changes in spatial patterns. In the presented example, differences in relative brightness across the scene are partially reproduced, indicating that the model learns spatio-temporal dynamics rather than simply propagating the last observation. However, this behavior is not consistent across all cases. We hypothesize that the model’s ability to predict spatial pattern changes depends on the presence of similar patterns within the context window. When comparable timesteps are

available, the model can leverage these as analogues to inform predictions. Consequently, longer context windows increase the likelihood of including relevant patterns, which may explain the observed improvements with increasing context length.

Figure 2. Temporal evolution of mean NDVI for a representative tile in the Czech Republic (cze_14.4937_50). Predicted and target NDVI values are averaged over all pixels per timestep. The mean predicted NDVI (blue), mean target NDVI (orange), and their difference (prediction – target, green) are shown.

Figure 3. Comparison of predicted and target NDVI for two representative timesteps ($t = 13$, 2019-07-23; $t = 16$, 2020-04-05) for a tile in the Czech Republic (cze_14.4937_50).

3.3 Limitations

Despite promising results, several limitations should be noted. First, evaluation is limited to a spatial split within Europe, without the temporal and spatial extrapolation tests proposed in Benson et al. (2024). Second, experiments are restricted to European data, despite the global coverage of GeoClimaData. Extending the analysis to diverse climatic regions would provide further insight into model generalization. Third, this study focuses on a single architecture (Contextformer) and does not include comparisons with alternative models. Therefore, we cannot assess whether the observed behavior generalizes to other architectures, or whether transformer-based models outperform alternative approaches under relaxed data conditions. Finally, this study still assumes fixed temporal context lengths and predefined aggregation strategies. However, recent work suggests that optimal temporal context may vary dynamically depending on the underlying processes and temporal scale of the signal (Koohfar & Dietz 2023). Incorporating adaptive or multi-scale context representations could help better capture both short-term variability and long-term trends, and represents a promising direction for future work.

4. Conclusion

In this study, we investigated the applicability of a benchmark-driven vegetation forecasting model under relaxed data conditions by applying Contextformer to irregularly sampled, multi-year EO-climate data. By systematically varying input design choices, we assessed the impact of context length, meteorological conditioning, and temporal and spatial encoding on predictive performance.

Our results show that Contextformer remains effective under irregular temporal sampling, outperforming a persistence baseline across all configurations. Increasing the context length provides modest but consistent gains, suggesting that longer temporal context can support vegetation forecasting by capturing ecological memory. In contrast, extending meteorological inputs beyond short-term windows degrades performance when temporal variability is lost through aggregation. Furthermore, replacing relative temporal encoding with explicit seasonal encoding does not improve performance, indicating that temporal information may already be implicitly captured through meteorological variables. Spatial encoding provides limited additional benefit under the current setup.

Overall, these results demonstrate that input design influences vegetation forecasting performance, with varying impact across components. The findings further suggest that models developed on standardized benchmarks can be adapted to more flexible EO datasets, provided that input representations are carefully considered. Future work should explore alternative meteorological encodings, global-scale evaluation, comparisons across model architectures, and the integration of adaptive or multi-scale temporal representations to better capture process-dependent dynamics.

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